

EFFECTIVENESS OF CLASSROOM COMMUNICATION AS A STRATEGY FOR AS A STRATEGY USED BY TEACHERS IN MANAGING STUDENTS' CLASSROOM MISBEHAVIOUR IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract: *The study determined the effectiveness of classroom communication as a strategy used by teachers in managing students' classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. One research question and one hypothesis guided the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 5,369 teachers in the 268 public secondary schools in the six-education zone in Anambra State. A sample of 378 was drawn using multistage sampling technique and simple random sampling. Two structured validated instruments were used for data collection. The reliability coefficients obtained was 0.87 for CCSQ and 0.83 for CMQ. Data analysis involved the use of mean and standard deviation to address the research questions. The findings of the study revealed that classroom communication is an effective strategy employed by teachers to manage students' misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The result showed that classroom communication used by teachers is significantly effective in managing students' misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on these findings, the following recommendations were made among others that teachers should collaboratively develop clear and concise rules with students at the beginning of each term to establish expectations and reduce the likelihood of students' classroom misbehaviour.*

Keywords: *Effectiveness, Classroom, Communication, Strategy, Misbehaviour*

Introduction

In secondary schools, students are placed at the core of teaching and learning processes, which aim to actively engage them in their educational journey. An ideal classroom environment promotes these opportunities by fostering open dialogue, group work and practical applications of knowledge, all of which contribute to a more enriched learning experience. In such an environment, students are expected to exhibit behaviour that supports a positive and productive learning atmosphere. This

includes respectful interaction with both teachers and fellow students. Additionally, students are expected to take responsibility for their own learning. This means coming to class prepared, completing assignments on time, and making a consistent effort to engage with the curriculum. Such behaviour ensures that students remain on track with their academic goals and encourages self-discipline and time management skills. Despite these clear expectations, challenges related to classroom misbehaviour occur.

Classroom misbehaviour is described as actions that are deemed inappropriate for the specific setting or situation in which they occur (Charles, 2018). Classroom misbehaviour is viewed as disruptive behaviour that violates the rules or unspoken norms of classroom conduct, requiring the teacher's intervention. Classroom misbehaviour disturbs the order of the class and hinders the teaching and learning process (Ajayi et al., 2017). It refers to any behaviour that interferes with the learning environment, such as students' failure to engage in activities, disrespect, excessive socialising, or partial involvement in tasks. Mbah (2020) categorized classroom misbehaviour as either overt or covert. Overt behaviours are visible and observable, such as talking during lessons, using mobile phones, or eating and drinking. Covert behaviours are more passive, like sleeping, arriving late, leaving early, or showing signs of boredom and disengagement during class.

Classroom misbehaviour significantly disrupts the teacher's ability to maintain order and hinders students' capacity to learn effectively. In Anambra State, this issue has become particularly problematic in public secondary schools. Various forms of misbehaviour have been observed, creating challenges in fostering a productive learning environment. According to Anyanwu et al. (2024), one major issue is a lack of respect towards teachers. Students often display rudeness, argue with educators, and disregard instructions, which undermines teacher authority. Another common form of misbehaviour involves disruptive conversations. As highlighted by Okafor (2015), this includes talking out of turn, making inappropriate remarks, and even assigning nicknames to teachers. Verbal altercations among students further contribute to the disruption (Anyanwu et al., 2024). These behaviours not only distract both teachers and learners but also slow the pace of lessons and negatively impact academic outcomes. This has increased the calls for the utilization of communication strategies by teachers.

Communication in the classroom involves the process of transmitting and receiving messages between teachers and students. It includes key elements such as the teacher (source), lesson content (message), the mode of communication (oral, written, or teaching aids), and the students (receivers). Effective communication is achieved when students understand and apply the knowledge gained to solve practical problems, while ineffective communication occurs when this understanding is lacking (Lewis, 2019). Effective communication is essential for classroom management and significantly impacts students' learning and motivation (Leonard et al., 2024). It also contributes to teachers' personal growth and career success, as highlighted by studies showing the importance of communication and teamwork skills in professional success (Morreale et al., 2020). Teachers with strong interpersonal and

communication skills enhance student motivation and understanding by simplifying complex ideas and tailoring their teaching to students' diverse strengths and weaknesses. Good communication combines receptive skills, such as understanding students' comprehension levels, and expressive skills, such as presenting ideas clearly (George et al., 2017; Utami, 2020). However, the level of effectiveness of communication strategies in managing classroom misbehaviour have not been empirically ascertained in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is against this backdrop that the researcher sought to investigate the effectiveness of classroom communication as a strategy used by teachers in managing students' classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Secondary education serves as a critical stage for equipping students with the knowledge and skills necessary for higher education and productive living. However, in recent times, there appear to be a growing concern about the rising incidence of classroom misbehaviour among secondary school students in Anambra State. This trend is particularly alarming in public secondary schools, where various forms of disruptive behaviours have been observed. The researcher's observations indicate an increasing prevalence of misbehaviours such as disrespect towards teachers, frequent disruptions during lessons, verbal altercations among students, and non-compliance with classroom rules. These behaviours not only hinder the learning process but also undermine the authority of teachers and disrupt the overall classroom environment. Given these challenges, the researcher is concerned about whether the communication strategies employed by teachers are effective in managing these behaviours. The increasing cases of classroom misbehaviour among students in public secondary schools, if not adequately addressed, could have far-reaching consequences on the quality of human capital being developed in Anambra State. It is against this backdrop that the researcher sought to investigate the effectiveness of classroom communication as a strategy used by teachers in managing students' classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the effectiveness of classroom communication as a strategy used by teachers in managing students' classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question

To what extent is classroom communication used by teachers as an effective strategy for managing students' classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

Classroom communication is not significantly effective for managing classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive research design, which was deemed appropriate as data was collected via questionnaires from teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was conducted in Anambra State, targeting a population of 5,369 teachers across 268 public secondary schools in the state's six education zones. Using Taro Yamane's formula, the sample size was determined to be 378 teachers, representing 7% of the total teacher population. A multistage random sampling technique was utilised to select the sample. First, three education zones—Ogidi, Nnewi, and Awka—were randomly chosen from the six zones. Next, two local government areas (LGAs) were randomly selected from each of the chosen zones: Idemili North and Idemili South from Ogidi Zone, Nnewi South and Ihiala from Nnewi Zone, and Aniocha and Awka South from Awka Zone. Proportionate stratified sampling was then used to determine the number of schools to be sampled in each LGA, resulting in three schools per LGA. Finally, simple random sampling was applied to select the specific schools, and all teachers in the chosen schools formed the study sample.

Two researcher-designed structured instruments were used for data collection: the Classroom Communication Strategies Questionnaire (CCSQ) and Classroom Misbehaviour Questionnaire (CMQ). The CCSQ contains 10 items on classroom communication. Items were rated on a four-point scale: Very Effective (VE), Effective (E), Ineffective (IE), and Very Ineffective (VIE). The CMQ consisted of 10 items assessing classroom misbehaviours, rated on a four-point scale: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), and Very Low Extent (VLE). To ensure validity, the instruments were reviewed by two experts in Educational Management and Policy Department and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation Unit of Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. They evaluated the instruments in relation to the study's objectives, research questions, and hypotheses. Reliability was established using the Cronbach Alpha method, with 20 copies of the questionnaires administered to teachers in two public secondary schools in Enugu State, which shares similar educational characteristics with Anambra State. The reliability coefficients obtained was 0.87 for CCSQ and 0.83 for CMQ. The questionnaires were distributed and retrieved by the researcher and three trained assistants using a direct delivery and retrieval approach. Of the 378 questionnaires distributed, 361 (95.50%) were properly completed and used for analysis, while 17 were either lost or incomplete. Data analysis involved the use of mean and standard deviation to address the research questions, with a 2.50 benchmark for effectiveness. Hypotheses were tested using paired t-test statistics at a significance level of $p > 0.05$. Items with a mean score of 2.50 and above were considered effective, while those below 2.50 were deemed ineffective. Null hypotheses were rejected when the calculated p-value was less than 0.05 and retained when greater than 0.05.

Results

Research Question

To what extent is classroom communication an effective strategy used by teachers for managing students’ classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Teachers on Effectiveness of Classroom Communication in Managing Students’ Misbehaviour in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State (N=361)

	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Listen to every student on any subject matter	2.96	0.76	Effective
2	Ensure my students understand my rules in a clear language	3.15	0.88	Effective
3	Learn the problems of students who frequently misbehave and provide guidance	3.27	0.85	Effective
4	Discuss the consequence of breaking the rules	3.38	0.78	Effective
5	Discuss rules; why a student should behave in a certain way	3.29	0.84	Effective
6	Provide clear guidelines so learners know expectations for behaviour in the class	3.44	0.82	Effective
7	Issue a warning to remind students of the rules	3.21	0.84	Effective
8	Invite parents of the misbehaving student and inform them of their child’s act	3.48	0.77	Effective
9	Recommend misbehaving student for counselling with the school’s students’ guidance counselor	3.30	0.79	Effective
10	Give feed back to the students on their performance	3.44	0.85	Effective
	Cluster Mean	3.29	0.82	Effective

Data in Table 1 showed that the respondents rated items 1-10 on classroom communication with mean ratings ranging between 2.96 and 3.48 as effective strategy for managing students’ classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The standard deviation scores ranging between 0.76 and 0.88 showed that the respondents’ opinions were related. The cluster mean of 3.02 indicated that classroom communication is an effective strategy used by teachers for managing students’ classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis

Classroom communication strategy is not significantly effective for managing classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 2: Test of Significance of Classroom Communication (CC) as Effective Strategy used by Teachers for Managing Students' Classroom Misbehaviour (SCM) in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Variables	N	Mean	std. dev.	t-value	Df	p-value	Decision
CC/SCM	361	3.38	0.772	33.443	360	.000	Significant

**Significant at $p < .05$*

Data in Table 2 showed the paired sample t-test of teachers on the significance of Classroom Communication (CC) in managing Students' Classroom Misbehaviour (SCM) in public secondary schools Anambra State. The result showed that the p-value of .000 is less than 0.05 level of significance which means that classroom communication used by teachers is significantly effective in managing students' misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on this result, the null hypothesis was not accepted. This means that classroom communication used by teachers is significantly effective in managing students' misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that classroom communication is an effective strategy employed by teachers to manage students' misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This outcome may stem from the significance of communication as a vital tool for fostering positive behaviour among students. This aligns with the findings of Utami (2020), who noted that teachers utilise a personal set of communication skills alongside various classroom management styles to address misbehaviour effectively. Utami (2020) further highlighted a significant variation in communication skills across different classroom management styles. The findings of this study also corroborate George et al. (2017) assertion that classroom communication aids teachers in establishing clear rules and procedures for acceptable classroom conduct. Similarly, the results are consistent with Karasova (2023) emphasis on the necessity of successful communication for effective learning. Specifically, effective communication in the classroom clarifies lesson content, making it easier for students to comprehend, while also reducing the teacher's workload as students understand the material more readily. Furthermore, the study demonstrated that secondary school teachers' use of classroom communication strategies is significantly effective in managing students' classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Conclusion

The researcher concludes that classroom communication is a highly effective strategy for managing students' classroom misbehaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The significance of

communication in establishing clear behavioural expectations and enhancing the understanding of lesson content is critical to fostering a conducive learning environment. The study confirms that effective communication strategies not only help in mitigating classroom misbehaviour but also simplify the teaching process and promote better student engagement. Consequently, the effective utilisation of communication strategies by teachers can lead to improved classroom management and enhanced learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teachers should collaboratively develop clear and concise rules with students at the beginning of each term to establish expectations and reduce the likelihood of students' classroom misbehaviour.
2. Teachers in public secondary schools should adopt interactive teaching methods that encourage student participation, reducing instances of misbehaviour by keeping students engaged.
3. Experienced teachers with strong communication and classroom management skills should mentor less experienced colleagues to share best practices and strategies.

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